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COVID-19 Special Issue-I

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Contents

Editorial	1
Articles	
Pandemic beyond Lockdown in India <i>Anirudha Barik & Balakrushna Padhi</i>	6
COVID-19 and Struggle for Survival of Informal Sector Workers: A Study of Street Vendors in Odisha <i>Minaketan Behera, Alok Ranjan Behera, Sibanarayan Mishra & Mohammed Imran</i>	25
COVID-19 and the Migrant Workers <i>Lopamudra Behera & Mitali Chinara</i>	50
COVID-19 in India: A Critical Assessment of Pandemic Modelling and Forecasting Gross Domestic Product Using ARMA <i>Madan Meher, Nikita Pradhan & Muralidhar Majhi</i>	74
Impact of COVID-19 on the Day-to-Day Life and Living of People: An Empirical Study in Chhattisgarh <i>Nilakantha Panigrahi & Rashmi Jaiswal</i>	100
Public Health Challenges and Management during the COVID-19 Outbreak in Odisha <i>Ashok Bhukta & Sudhakar Patra</i>	125
Out-migration from Odisha: An Analysis in the Wake of COVID-19 Crisis <i>Manas Kumar Pedi & Kshamanidhi Adabar</i>	137

Editorial

I Introduction

It would be no exaggeration to assert that one of the gravest health calamities that the world has had to encounter over the past hundred years is the present COVID-19 pandemic that is still very much upon us. On the day of writing this overview, 11th December 2020, the world has already recorded around 69.6 million cases, with about 1.6 million deaths. Of these, India's share has been 9.8 million and 1.4 lakh, respectively. In absolute terms these numbers are already rather high. Owing to the nature of the corona virus, which has a very high possibility of community spread, virtually all countries of the world have had to undertake and enforce prolonged periods of lockdowns and closures of schools, colleges, government offices, courts, market places, and other places of public gathering. In many countries, including India, industries have had to shut down, and most modes of transport have had to be very severely curtailed. The impact of all this on economic activity has been devastating. In the first quarter, April-June of 2020-21, the Indian economy shrank by an unprecedented 23.9 percentage points. The rest of the world also has had to bear the fury of the pandemic in varying degrees.

The COVID-19 pandemic has not merely posed a threat to life but also livelihoods at large. It has already brought about substantial loss of lives and job losses in the US and other major West European countries. Its fatality quotient in the developing world has fortunately been weak. However, its spread potential is perhaps the most in these parts, given the living conditions and environment of the developing world. Appearing in the scene since eight months, its spread remains unabated while the treatment protocol seems to be, at best, tentative.

The possibility of a vaccine, however, seems to be emerging in the horizon. Given the asymptomatic nature of this infection, it has rather made it impossible to ascertain its real grip over the population and that has led to umpteen sets of safety measures to be in place, which has not only crippled the means of living for many, but has also brought about a changing order of living termed as new normal. While one is not sure as yet as to how long it is going to sustain its threat over humanity, the alternative order of living,

the nature of exchanges as well as societal arrangements at large seem to be responding, though only very slowly or in a gradual manner. One needs to perhaps rewrite the common scheme of things with regulations and protocols which were otherwise hitherto overlooked.

II The pandemic and its bearing on the economy and society

In the absence of a definite course of treatment for this infection as well as its protection through vaccination, emphasis has been laid on its containment. The containment measures are in terms of lockdown, social distancing and adoption of proper hygiene practices to keep the infection at bay. While these measures undoubtedly can arrest the spread of infection to a reasonable extent, one wonders as to its implementation in the prevailing living environment on one hand and its differential consequences on various population segments on the other. Measures like social distancing and lockdown seem to be emerging from a middle class mindset that overlooks the larger reality of life and livelihood of the masses. In fact, such containment measures are not only having a 'privilege' bias, but they have also compromised the state of living of a large share of our population that is least resilient to bear the brunt of the changing order of life.

Imposition of such measures have brought to the fore many aspects that were otherwise overlooked, like basic needs, social protection, and resilience to with stand shocks arising out of the unprecedented situation. A country with a billion plus population was for the first time made aware of its vulnerabilities when it had to put up with the chaos that emerged while fighting this pandemic. The vulnerabilities included compromised state of living in urban spaces, a predominant workforce in the unorganised sector without any protection whatsoever and, above all, the limited duration of survival without paid work. Apart from these vulnerabilities, the health infrastructure with a skewed public-private divide is far from sufficient to handle such eventualities. The disparate distribution of health workforce across regions added to the woes further. Given these vulnerabilities, the reading and understanding of the trajectories that the economy is going to assume gained utmost significance. While the immediate implications were in terms of protection of the masses through provisioning of means of survival, the renewal of economic activities in many sectors poses a grave challenge given the pre-COVID-19 work environment, alongside the predominance of informal nature of work.

The pandemic has given rise to a multiplicity of issues cutting across sectors, and is going to leave a scar that would last for quite long. The threat of its spread enforces a different order of living and functioning that has enforced alternative means of conducting routine affairs in almost all sectors. The most visible departure has been from the real to the virtual, personal to impersonal, and the vehicle for this has been the digital interface. It becomes therefore pertinent to engage in understanding its impact on various facets of the economy and society. The *Orissa Economic Journal*, being an instrument of exposition on the concurrent changes in the economy and society, makes a pitch for engagement with this unprecedented circumstance through its pages wherein thoughts and opinions are presented with contributions relating to specific domains. The twin foci have been on the health sector and the economy.

As regards the economy, there are a varied set of propositions that are made in terms of the consequences and sector specific impacts. While the economy has taken the worst beating in terms of shrinking GDP, rising unemployment along with a threat of recession, scholars in this issue have made scientific attempts at forecasting the GDP in times of such a crisis. Such a reading of the economy considering the emerging circumstances undoubtedly provides an expected trajectory of the regional and the national economy. Besides this assessment, attempts have been made to analyse selected sectors of the economy considering the extent of informality therein that brings to the fore the kind of vulnerability associated with the prevailing informality in the Indian economy. This not only calls for reducing informality to a great extent but also provides a ground for the kind of protection that is essential in many of these sectors.

Another segment of papers which largely focus on the health sector comprises challenges posed by the pandemic to the prevailing health system in general and public health outlook in particular. This also includes a region specific assessment of imposition of preventive measures of containing the pandemic among the masses wherein the impracticality of such measures to be effective on the ground along with the lack of feasibility to adhere to such measures have been discussed. When it comes to the health system response, the obvious inadequacy of the infrastructure and its regional disparities are also highlighted. In fact, these analyses of the situation implicitly or explicitly emphasise the role of inter-sectoral coordination that

becomes handy in such emergencies. The set of contributions undoubtedly highlight the vulnerability of the informal work force, inadequacy of health system infrastructure, and also the need for recognition of the distressed migration for the state for employment. While these are not new, their analytic exposition and consequential features offer added evidence to act towards making things better to confront similar challenges in future.

III Some Specific Cases

The contributions made in the volume are not only informative but also can serve towards understanding the economy from wide ranging perspectives. Some of the unique perspectives may be mentioned here. First, COVID-19 has impacted the education sector at large, and the schools and colleges in particular, to a very significant extent. Most educational institutions have remained closed. There is a study that looks at the E-Vidya Programme in the KBK (Kalahandi-Balangir-Koraput) districts. After COVID-19 most classes moved into the online mode. The author however points out that only about 5 to 8 per cent households in the urban areas and barely 2 per cent in the rural areas possess laptops and have access to the internet. Under the present circumstances, therefore, the online teaching programme in these poor far flung districts are bound to be a failure. Another case study looks at the impact of COVID-19 on the handloom sector in Odisha. There are about 1.18 lakh handloom workers in the state. It is revealing to note that as many as 89% of the handloom workers earn less than Rs 5000 per month, and their families live in rather precarious conditions. The onset of COVID-19 has resulted in nil demand for their products, which has intensified their financial difficulties.

IV Concluding Remarks

The COVID-19 pandemic has provided a unique vantage point to reflect on the nature of social and economic development that the world has witnessed after the onset of Industrial Revolution in the middle of the eighteenth century in England and some of the major European countries. By the time Adam Smith published his *Wealth of Nations* in 1776, he had already witnessed and theorised about the clear advantages of 'division of labour' and specialisation. By the beginning of the nineteenth century, England was dotted with hundreds of factories. Labour was being drawn from agriculture to work in factories. The factory owners, or the capitalists,

were out to maximise their profits, and this was realised at the cost of labourers living in appalling conditions in industrial townships. Man was out to conquer nature and produce goods and services at a fast pace to satisfy human wants. This however led to a massive destruction of the flora and fauna. Such an emerging development trajectory was already evident to some of the later classical masters such as John Stuart Mill.

In his *Principles of Political Economy* published in 1848 Mill argued against the singular focus on economic growth and boldly welcomed a stationary state. He imagined a state where there would be a stable population and thanks to technical innovations, people in general would be assured of a comfortable existence. Mill saw this as the beginning of a benign world where mankind would turn its attention to the serious and meaningful matters of liberty and justice, so that all individuals are able to realise their full potential. After a few weeks' lockdown there have been innumerable instances of rejuvenation and renewal of natural phenomena within India and across the globe. The quality of water in the Ganges distinctly improved, and the snow-capped peaks of the Himalayas could be seen from cities like Jalandhar after more than a hundred years!

What we are trying to emphasise, in other words, is that one of the unexpected fallouts of the COVID-19 pandemic is the vital truth that humans need to respect nature and learn to live in harmony with natural phenomena. This would also call for revisiting the scope of age old subjects of study like economics.

The editors of this volume would like to applaud the initiative of the Orissa Economic Association to publish this special issue on the economic and social implications of the COVID-19 pandemic. The contributors have addressed diverse aspects of the economic fallouts of COVID-19 as it has affected the state of Odisha in particular. It is hoped that these essays will help us understand the nature of this major calamity in a more informed manner.

Pulin B. Nayak and Udaya S. Mishra

COVID-19 and Struggle for Survival of Informal Sector Workers: A Study of Street Vendors in Odisha

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Abstract

COVID-19 is an existential threat to the health and livelihood of millions of people working in the informal sector. This pandemic is an exceptional shock for the poor workers. They are the most vulnerable group as they depend on daily wages to meet their ends. Still, today their affordability of three meals per day seems burdensome. Street vending is a part of the informal economy. It has been one of the important sources of income and employment for informal sector workers. Poverty and lack of employment in Odisha's rural areas force people to migrate to urban areas searching for work and livelihood. The large numbers of urban poor people in Bhubaneswar, Odisha, survive through working as street vendors. This paper aims to assess the impact of COVID-19 on street vendors in Odisha during the state-enforced lockdown and analyse the government's policies to address COVID-19 for this sector. It also recommends some measures to help minimize the pandemic's social and economic impact on these workers.

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Both primary and secondary sources of data have been used for this study. The primary data has been generated through fieldwork employing a survey method with a structured and semi-structured interview schedule with a sample size of 110 street vendors from Bhubaneswar. This paper shows that the employment and income of street vendors are severely affected by the current pandemic.

Keywords: Street vendors, COVID-19, Income reduction, Living condition, Bhubaneswar

1. Introduction

Poverty and lack of job opportunities in rural and smaller towns drive many families to cities for employment and livelihood. In general, these migrant workers have low skills and lack the education needed for better-paid employment in the structured or formal sectors. Furthermore, formal sector jobs are shrinking. They need to create their own employment to join the urban economy through entry-level professions that require little capital and few skills. Street vending has been one of the easiest ways to survive for the urban poor and is widespread in the urban informal sector. In a broad sense, a street vendor is defined as a person who offers goods to the public without having a permanent build-up from where he sells (Bhowmik & Saha, 2012). They are mobile in the sense they move from place to place carrying their products on temporary cart or by cycle or in the baskets on their head. The National Policy of Urban Street Vendors (NPUSV) 2004, Government of India defined street vendors as "A street vendor is broadly defined vendor as a person who offers goods for sale to the public without a permanent built up structure but with a temporary static structure or mobile stall (or head load)". The trading of these informal sector workers is generally stationary and mobile. The informal sector workers are broadly classified into three groups: wage workers in the informal sector, self-employed workers, and unprotected wage workers in the informal sector (Chen et al., 2002, NCEUS 2007). And street vendors are identified as self-employed urban informal sector workers (Saha, 2009). Street vending is an important livelihood securing sector for the urban poor. It offers lower middle and working-class seasonal employment and has been their source of income.

The street vendor concept is there from the time of human civilization. In ancient and medieval civilization, they were recognised as travelling

merchants who travelled from town to town to sold their products and traded in neighbouring countries (Bhowmik & Saha, 2012). They were well regarded at that time, but street vendors are rarely treated with the same dignity and tolerance in the modern period. Despite being the oldest retailing form, India's urban laws still neglect this activity and people involved in this activity (Jha, 2018). Police and municipality officials in urban areas often target them for blocking pavements and creating traffic problems. Even the middle-class residents complain about them for creating disturbances to their general life, though they mostly prefer to buy products from them due to low price (Bhowmik & Saha, 2012). Thus, uncertainties of the business are often present as officials continuously harass them. This group faces different social protection problems, credit accessibility, working conditions, and public space utilization (Bhowmik, 2001; Anjaria, 2006). They are the most vulnerable workers group in the unorganized sector of any developing or underdeveloped economy as their income is low and uncertain and creates anxiety in many aspects (Baliyan & Srivastava, 2016; Kumar & Shing, 2009).

A street vendor is an important component of the urban informal economy (Chakraborty & Koley, 2018; Sharma & Konwar, 2014). Nearly 2.5 per cent of India's population depends upon street vending as a source of livelihood (Kumar & Shing, 2009). Street vendors constitute 11 per cent of the total urban employment in India (Chen et al., 2013). So, street vending is a large employment source in towns and cities of developing countries (Choudhury et al., 2011). Poverty and lack of employment opportunities in rural and small towns drive a group of people to cities searching for better work and livelihood (Pushpalatha & Punnavanam, 2020). However, due to lack of skill and education, they could not get satisfactory employment. Thus, they prefer to work through any means to feed their family as well as themselves. One option left to do so for them is street vending, and they start to sell products outside with a low level of investment. Thus, in the current scenario, street vending is an imperative and integral part of urban employment (Baliyan & Srivastava, 2016). The spreading of this deadly virus is increasing at a higher rate worldwide and has 38 million confirmed cases. India and Odisha in the initial stage had a slower spreading rate, but recently it is drastically increasing. In India, the confirmed cases have reached 69.04 lakh, and in Odisha, it has reached 2.4 lakh as of October 14, 2020. The rate of increase in cases is detrimental for the state and building an alarming condition. So from this point of view, Bhubaneswar having a unique socio-cultural and economic setting is an ideal place for the present paper, which intends to understand the socio-economic impact of the COVID-19 outbreak on marginalized sections of the urban society, namely

street vendors, during the lockdown. It focuses on how do we get them back on track and make our systems resilient to deal with such crises in the future.

The paper is divided into six sections. After the introduction in section I, section II summarises the origin of COVID-19 and Odisha's COVID Profile. Section III gives a brief overview of street vendors in India and Odisha, followed by the impact of COVID-19 on street vendors in section IV. The Odisha government's response to COVID-19 affecting street vendors is discussed in section V, while the possible road ahead after COVID 19 for street vendors is given in section VI.

Informal Sector and India: An Overview

The 15th International Conference of Labour Statisticians (ICLS) in 1993 defined the informal sector as "A group of production units comprised of unincorporated enterprises owned by households, including informal own-account enterprises and enterprises of informal employers (typically small and non-registered enterprises)" (ILO, 1993). However, this definition was limited to enterprises only. Therefore, after ten years, in the 17th ICLS in 2003, the definition of informal employment was redefined and introduced in a broader concept as "Informal employment refers to employment arrangements that leave individuals without legal or social protection and, hence, more exposed to economic risk than others, whether or not the economic units they are working for or which they own are formal enterprises, informal enterprises or households" (ILO, 2003). So, informal workers are those whose social security is not paid by the employer, and they are not entitled to get paid annual or sick leave. The job security and social protection of these workers are not there. These workers are desperate enough to work at a subsistence wage to fulfill their minimum family requirements as they are low skilled for work. They are mainly working in different parts of the country as daily wage earners, salesmen in shops, factory workers, construction workers, and also as more than 100 million landless agricultural workers (Radhakrishnan, 2020).

The term "informal sector" is used explicitly by W Arthur Lewis in his economic development theory to explain employment and livelihood generation in the developing world (Pushpalatha & Punnavanam, 2020). Though the informal sector constitutes a significant portion of the developing economy, its real existence is not clear as it is unreported by employers for their ill-treatment. Informal workers work in miserable conditions. The

occupational and health safety of these workers is not taken into consideration. They are facing inadequate access to water, sanitation, and risk management in the working environment. These workers are also facing financial problems in the form of the lower-wage rate and insecurity in payment receipts.

As per the International Labour Organization (ILO), close to 81 per cent of all employed persons in India is engaged in the informal sector, with only 6.5 per cent in the formal sector and 0.8 per cent in the household sector (ILO, 2018). The employment scenario in different countries is also different. In low-income countries, informal employment represents 90 per cent of total employment, in middle-income countries, 67 per cent and 18 per cent in high-income countries (ILO, 2018). The Economic Survey of India 2018-19 estimates that almost 93 per cent of the total workforce is employed in the informal sector. The layout of informal workers is gloomier as it grows in an unorganized manner. The Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS) of 2017-18 released in May 2019 indicates that even 71.1 per cent of regular wage/salaried workers in the non-agricultural sector (of the informal sector) had no written job contract, 54.2 per cent were not eligible for paid leave and eligibility for any social security benefit was not there of 49.6 per cent of the workers. They are deprived of the benefit of safety equipment at the workplace, medical facility, or family welfare support, a minimum standard of wage, and specification to certain working hours. So, they are exploited by employers in different forms. They are usually paid at a low rate ranging from Rs.400 to Rs.1000 (US\$5 to US\$13) and that too on a daily basis. So, the scope for saving is almost zero for them and even access to financial institutions is not proper.

2. Review of literature

Street vending is an integral part of the urban informal economy. Street vending has survived for a long time as there is an increasing demand from the middle class in urban areas as they get inexpensive goods from street vendors compared to malls and organized stores (Kumar, 2015). Still, some people often complain about street vendors and ill-treat them as they block pavements and are less concerned about sanitary measures at the place (Bhowmik & Saha, 2012). Street vendors make the street safer for women (SHRAM, 2015). However, these vendors are facing many difficulties in their lives and livelihood.

Poverty and illiteracy are forcing rural poor to move from rural to urban

cities/towns for better job opportunities and livelihood. The non-availability of alternative jobs necessitates them to choose street vending as the source of livelihood (NIDAN, 2010). Free entry to the market and low level of investment required for trading are other reasons for choosing street vending by these people (Pushpalatha & Punnavanam, 2020; NIDAN, 2010). As a result, the number of street vendors in cities has increased over the years, but the space for vending is limited (Jha, 2018). This is becoming a burden and hindrance to urban planning by authorities (Chen et al., 2013). Consequently, many of these vendors are harassed by local authorities and police (Saha, 2011; NIDAN, 2010; Bhowmik, 2001). The fear of police attacks is always present among vendors (Chen et al., 2013). For this reason, they give bribe to officials and police to be protected from short-term attacks (Bhowmik & Saha, 2012). Corruption in the form of bribery and extortion eats into these people's earning and reduces their income further (Bhowmik, 2001). Often, the wastage of products by officials and police gives them a huge loss in earning (Sekar, 2008; Phil, 2010). These workers work excessive hours for economic activity (Saha, 2011; Sekar, 2008). And the majority of them do not use safety equipment at workplace (Pushpalatha & Punnavanam, 2020). To solve these problems, there is a need to regularize street vending in the country.

An institutional mechanism needs to be developed in such a way which will protect the interest of street vendors. For example, the model implemented by Bhubaneswar Public-Private Community Partners (PPCP) legitimizes street vending and gives rise to a sustainable market to millions of vendors to earn from the street (Kumar & Shing, 2009). However, in the case of policy implementation, the same states take quick decisions while others take longer (Sinha & Roever, 2011). So, there is a lack of uniformity in the functioning of street vendors across states. Regularising street vendors will help those people in different forms. The social, mental, and financial conditions of these vendors will be improved by regularising them. On one hand, they need not give a bribe (hafta), and on the other hand, they can access institutional finance (SHRAM, 2015). By this, they can be kept out from the exploitation of money lenders on whom they are mostly dependent for economic and social activity (Saha, 2011). For operating the business, most finance is derived from their own saving, which is small (Bhowmik & Saha, 2012). So, formalisation of street vendors is required all over the country for which licensing of vendors is important. By this, the fear of attack by police or any kind of public disturbances could be avoided. However, municipality authorities are reluctant to issue a license to them

(Bhowmik, 2001), and often, they demand bribes from them. So, it becomes challenging to procure a license the official side, and also from the vendor side to apply for license properly as they are less educated (Sekar, 2008; NIDAN, 2010; Bhowmik, 2001).

In street vending, gender is also an issue. There is dominance of male street vendors in the market (Bhowmik & Saha, 2012). This is because a female vendor faces more problems than a male vendor (Baliyan & Srivastava, 2016). The street is a public and crowded place. The dominance of male vendors restricts female vendors from getting a suitable tradable space in the market. Due to the non-availability of reserved space, a female vendor cannot continue for a long period due to lack of buyers (Sharma & Konwar, 2014). So, the numbers of male vendors are more than female and live in better conditions with respect to income (Chakraborty & Koley, 2018). So, there is a “decent work deficit” in the working life of street vendors (Saha, 2011).

In any kind of uncertain situation, street vendors are affected badly. In the case of natural disasters like floods or cyclones, they are highly affected as their shops are stationary or not well built. Taking into consideration the current undesirable situation of COVID-19, street vendors are severely affected. A study by the Institute of Social Studies Trust (ISST) indicates that 97.14 per cent of vendors are adversely affected by lockdown. The fear of disease or lack of protective equipment is the main reason for slow trade, and consequently, fall in income (ISST, 2020). So, there is a need to look into this vulnerable group of the economy.

3. Materials and Methods

The present study has been conducted on the impact of COVID-19 on street vendors in Bhubaneswar, Odisha. Both primary and secondary sources of data have been used for this study. Primary data has been generated through fieldwork by using survey method with structured and semi-structured interview schedule. Simultaneously, group discussions and informal interview methods have been used. Observation has been done through semi-participant methods. A total of 110 street vendors have been surveyed from Bhubaneswar. The secondary sources of data used in the study are from the Census of India, Economic Survey of Odisha, Government of Odisha, Reports of NSSO, and NCEUS. In addition to the documents, various books, journals, and newspapers are referred to and used. The variables used in this paper are based on the impact of COVID-19 on street vendors on various dimensions and issues. Different data are presented in tabular form, which is shown in percentage.

1. Results and Discussion

Number of Street Vendors in India and Odisha

There are conflicting estimates on the number of street vendors in India's cities. There are about 10 million street vendors throughout India with Mumbai accounting for 250,000, Delhi has 200,000, Kolkata, more than 150,000, and Ahmedabad, 100,000 as per the Ministry of Housing and Urban Poverty Alleviation. The Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihood and Regulation of Street Vending) Act, 2014 calculates a maximum of 2.5 per cent of a city's population as street vendors. The National Census 2011 put the national urban population at 377 million. Assuming that the urban population now stands at around 430 million, there will currently be approximately 10 million street vendors. However, this figure seems to be on the higher side, considering the results of successive rounds of the census conducted by the National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO). Notwithstanding the variations in the successive NSSO rounds since 1983, the urban population with street vendors as their primary occupation has grown from 1.03 million in 1983 to 1.61 million in 2011-12. This is not close to even half of the calculations under the Street Vending Act and the number presumed by the National Policy. The data shows 3.33 million persons (urban plus rural) involved in street vending as their primary occupation, which, too, is significantly lesser than the estimated mark. There are 65,000 registered street vendors in Odisha. With more urbanisation likely to happen across India, the number of street vendors is expected to rise substantially.

Table 1: Number of Street Vendors, All India (1983-2012)

Year	Rural	Urban	Total
1983	1081629	1034744	2116373
1987-88	837684	943801	1781485
1993-94	1292906	1344467	2637373
1999-2000	967853	1088241	2056094
2004-05	2137056	2508987	4646043
2011-12	1721215	1614428	3335643

Source: NSSO, 2011-12

Profile of the Sample Street Vendors in Odisha

In this study, we have shown the socio-economic condition of street vendors. The study found 80 per cent of Hindu street vendors and 20 per cent of muslim vendors, most of whom are engaged in activities like chicken, mutton, and fish. In the context of caste, 36per cent, 30per cent, and 34 per cent of the vendors are from general, OBC, and SC categories, respectively. From marriage point of view, majority (63%) of the vendors are married. Though some of the vendors are unmarried, most of the vendors live with their family with an average family size of 5 members. So, many people in the family depend on the earnings of these vendors. Every vendor has a huge responsibility of sustaining their family.

Figure 1: Gender Composition of Vendors

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The occupation of street vending is mostly dominated by male vendors, as shown by the study. We found only 7 per cent female vendors in our study. Violence and male domination on the street or hardship of work has discouraged female vendors from this occupation. Those who are still working in this field are facing many difficulties in their day-to-day life.

Table: 2 Education Profiles of Vendors

Education	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	13	11.83
Primary	51	46.36
Secondary	32	29.09
Higher secondary	14	12.72
Total	110	100

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The education profile of street vendors is very low. The maximum of vendors are primarily literate (46%) or illiterate. None of them have obtained higher education, and very few have obtained higher secondary education (13%). So, these vendors are educationally backward and less technical efficient. This is one of the reasons for choosing street vending as an occupation by this group of people.

Figure 2: Reasons for Choosing Street Vending as Occupation

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Street vending is an occupation which lacks social dignity and prestige. However, still a large group of the population chooses this occupation for different reasons. Parental occupation (25%), not getting any work (27%), and own interest in it (21%), are the main reasons for choosing street vending as occupation. In a situation of lack of technical efficiency and partially stationary vending set-up, parents encourage their children to take up the same job. Likewise, some people do not get any job due to low levels of education and technical inefficiency; with no option left, they choose street vending as their occupation. Loss of job, financial problem, and low level of education are also reasons for choosing street vending as an occupation. Among the respondents, some are working for long days, and some of them have newly started this occupation. Table 3 depicts a picture of how long they are in the street vending occupation.

Table 3: Street Vending - Since How Long

Years	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1	10	9.1
1-5	22	20
5-10	39	35.45
10-15	22	20
15-20	9	8.18
More than 20	8	7.27
Total	110	100

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The study found that many of the vendors are doing this for a long time while some started pursuing this occupation recently. With the changing economic situation and employment profile, some people prefer to do only street vending. Some vendors are into this occupation for a long time, either for better income or they have a semi shop-like structure. There are different categories of vendors. Street vendors are categorised according to the goods they sell in the street. The profile of these vendors is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Category of Street Vendors

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The study found 14 categories of street vendors as mentioned in figure 3. The majority of street vendors under the purview of our study are fruit sellers, vegetable sellers, and street food and fish, chicken, and mutton sellers with percentages of 8.18, 13.64, 12.73, and 16.36, respectively. There are also other different sellers like tea, lassi & juice, flowers, books, magazines, etc. Due to the spread of corona virus and the increasing demand for masks and sanitizer, some people have started to sell these products on the street. The new traffic rules have increased demand for helmets in the market. Thus, some people have started to sell helmets on the street. However, the working hours vary in different street vending, which is shown in table 4.

Table 4: Working Hour and Category of Vendors

Category of vendors	Working hours			Total
	< 7 hours	7-10 hour	> 10 hours	
Fruits	0	5	4	9
Vegetable	6	8	1	15
Street food	1	7	6	14
Fish, chicken, mutton	6	10	2	18
Tea, lassi, juice	0	4	5	9
Flower	3	2	3	8
Stationery products	0	3	8	11
Sweets	0	1	3	4
Books and magazines	0	0	3	3
Mobile cover	0	4	0	4
Cycle and tyre repairing	0	0	4	4
Mushroom	2	3	0	5
Mask and sanitizer	0	3	0	3
Helmet	0	1	2	3
Total	18 (16.37)	51 (46.36)	41 (37.27)	110

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The working hours in the informal sector are a big issue for workers. However, it varies according to different kinds of job. In our study, working hour is grouped into three categories, namely less hours (less than 7 hours), medium hours (7-10 hours), and very long hours (more than 10 hours). About 37 per cent of street vendors work for more than 10 hours, which is a long period. More particularly, street food sellers, cycle & tyre repairing shop, stationery products sellers work for a long duration. Working for longer hours deteriorates the health and mental condition of workers.

Figure 3: Source of Initial Capital

Source: Field Survey, 2020

For any kind of business, there is need for capital. And the installation capital is a bit higher. Figure 3 depicts that 55 per cent of vendors had started their trading with the help of their own savings. Some vendors had started their trading by borrowing from relatives (34%) and money lenders (11%). In terms of monthly income, 36 per cent of vendors have an income of less than Rs. 10000 and 24 per cent of vendors earn low income of Rs. 10000-15000, particularly, in vending related to vegetables, books & magazines, tea, lassi & juice, and mobile. However, vendors selling street food, fish, chicken & mutton earn a comparatively better income. So, there is variation in earning as per the category of vending. However, many of them are not satisfied with their occupation. Figure 4 shows us job satisfaction and reasons for lack of satisfaction in vendors.

Table 5: Monthly Income and Category of Vendors

Category of vendors	Monthly income (in Rs.)				Total
	Less than 10000	10000-15000	15000-20000	20000 above	
Fruits	1	2	6	0	9
Vegetable	7	3	5	0	15
Street food	0	5	5	4	14
Fish, chicken, mutton	2	0	10	6	18
Tea, lassi, juice	4	2	1	2	9
Flower	5	3	0	0	8
Stationary products	4	2	5	0	11
Sweets	2	2	0	0	4
Books and magazine	2	1	0	0	3
Mobile cover	4	0	0	0	4
Cycle and tyre repairing	1	3	0	0	4
Mushroom	3	2	0	0	5
Mask and sanitizer seller	3	0	0	0	3
Helmet	2	1	0	0	3
Total	40 (36.36)	26 (23.64)	32 (29.09)	12 (10.91)	110

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Figure 4: Job Satisfaction and Reasons for Not Being Satisfied

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The majority of street vendors (52 per cent) are not satisfied with their job. As per the study, three main reasons for non-satisfaction are long working hours, not working in a good environment, and low income. About 63 per cent of unsatisfied vendors mentioned that low income is the reason for the non-satisfaction in their job. Along with this, street vendors face other challenges in their day-to-day life, shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Challenges in Street Vending

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Street vendors are insecure about their trading places, business volume, and many others. There is always a fear among them about police attack. Uncertain weather also affects their trading as well as wastage of their goods. So, there is an insecurity of trade among street vendors. In response to this, 66 per cent of vendors agreed that they are insecure about their trade. Officials, police and even the public harass the street vendors. However, harassment of vendors is low (17 per cent) in the study area. Another challenge faced by street vendors is the hard and long hours of work. In our study, 72 per cent of vendors said that they worked hard and for long hours.

Due to spread of Corona virus and lockdown, every group of society has been affected, and street vendors are one of them. Street vendors are one of the most vulnerably affected groups. The total trading of these people has been highly affected. The income and employment profile of these people has drastically reduced. Due to the lockdown to prevent the spread of the Corona virus, the trading of street vendors has been affected. Among the

studied street vendors, 95.45 per cent of vendors said that their income has been affected. These are vendors who have returned to their vending, but some other vendors have not started vending till now. So, the effect is much greater than this. Among affected vendors, there are different reasons for which their vending has been affected, which are shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Reasons for Income Being Affected

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The income of street vendors has been affected due to different reasons, as mentioned in the above figure. The most important reason is fewer customers on the street. Due to the fear of the virus, people are not coming outside for any kind of purchase. More particularly, people are avoiding places like the street, where generally crowds gather and sanitary measures are not properly maintained. So, street vendors are facing a lack of demand for their product, due to which their income has reduced. Initially, there was a complete lockdown in our country, during which vendors could not sell their goods. However, after some relaxation, some vendors started their trade, but sales were not as good as earlier due to weekend shutdown, restriction on time, police attack in small crowded places, and many others. So, 13 per cent of vendors stated that shutdown and police restrictions are the reasons for decline in income. Another important reason is the transportation problem. Generally, products like fruits, vegetables, and fish are brought from distant places to urban areas. Due to the spread of virus, the transportation sector has alone been affected. Thus, vendors are not getting a sufficient amount of products to sell. For this reason, 15 per cent of vendors mentioned that transportation problem is the reason for decline

in income. Some vendors also said that both lockdown/shut down and fewer customers are the reasons for decline in income. The decline in amount of income is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Income Changes Due to Corona Lockdown

Category of vendors	Average income of February	Average income reduced	Percentage of reduction
Fruits	9889	1445	14.6
Vegetable	9400	1200	12.76
Street food	11357	7000	61.63
Fish, chicken, mutton	11055	4277	38.68
Tea, lassi, juice	10111	2445	24.18
Flowers	4875	2875	58.97
Stationary products	8636	5090	58.93
Sweets	12500	6250	50
Books and magazine	11333	5666	50
Mobile cover	11000	8000	72.72
Cycle and tyre repairing	12250	8250	67.34
Mushroom	10000	4500	45
Mask and sanitiser seller ¹	4666	2666	57.13
Helmet	9000	7333	81.47
Total	9827	4236	43.10

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Table 4 depicts a clear picture of the income profile of street vendors according to their category. February is considered as a normal period and June as lockdown period. We can see that the monthly average income of street vendors at aggregate level was Rs. 9827 before the spread of Corona virus. During the shutdown period, on average, there was income of Rs. 4236, showing a 43 per cent decline. More particularly, sellers of street food, helmet, mobile cover, and cycle & tyre repairing shops have drastically reduced. Demand for street foods declined as the sellers are rarely concerned about sanitary measures. There is uncertainty about the volume of sales at present. So, the sellers do not have a large volume of sales but at the same time, they are incurring increased costs. The income of these vendors has been highly reduced. Due to newly traffic rules, demand for the helmet was high, and these sellers used to earn a good income. However, due to

COVID-19, very few people are stepping outside their homes. As a result, helmet sales has nearly stopped, and so has the income for these vendors. The situation is almost the same for cycle and tyre repair shops.

The income of fruit and vegetable sellers has declined, but not greatly. Even at the start of the lockdown with high restrictions, fruits and vegetable selling was permitted in the market. However, these sellers suffered in two ways, first due to transportation problem, and also due to decreasing demand in the market. Thus, the income of fruit and vegetable vendors has declined by 14.6 per cent and 12.76 per cent, respectively. The income of fish, chicken, and mutton vendors has declined by 39 per cent. People do not find it necessary to consume these items, for which they have to go outside. So, in general, due to fewer customers and fewer sales, the income of these vendors has reduced. Likewise, every vendor has suffered in this situation. The income of every vendor has reduced due to different reasons. Thus, the spread of Corona virus has a negative impact on the income of street vendors.

Field Observation

It is observed from the current situation that more than 50 per cent of street vendors have not returned to their occupation even after the unlock process started in the country. Many peanut, idol, and plastic flower sellers were seen everywhere in the city before COVID-19, but nowadays, they have completely vanished from the market. This is because they belonged to North India, especially Uttar Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh, and they have all moved to their native place. The same happened with door screen seller, clay pot seller, light seller, hakimi medicine seller (jadi buti), and astrologer. Likewise, few street food vendors are seen in the market, and this number was very high before COVID-19 in the city. The situation is the same for all kinds of street vendors and many reasons behind this. Some demand-side and some supply-side factors are responsible for it. A few street vendors are reluctant to vend because of the fear of disease, pressure from their house, and some depend upon educational institutions. Due to COVID-19, all educational institutions are closed up to October 31, 2020 as declared by the state government of Odisha. People also do not feel safe to move

¹Mask and sanitiser are highly in demand in recent days. So many vendors prefer them; this is a newly emerging activity. The income for February is taken from their previous job.

outside and buy street foods. So, vendors are facing a lack of demand for their products, which prevents them from engaging in vending activity. The role of street vendors is important for the recovery of the economy hit by COVID-19. However, the sector itself is gravely affected to such an extent that the dynamics of restructuring to normal is becoming difficult. The functioning of trade is getting strenuous. Even the nutrition in food intake has reduced and paying monthly rent is becoming tough (Kesar et al., 2020). Thus, it can be stated that street vendors have been severely affected by COVID-19.

Anil Kumar Das, a 22-year-old is working as a street vendor in the Rasulgarh area of Bhubaneswar. He has completed his 12th standard in Science from Ekamra College in Bhubaneswar after completing his technical course. He went to Bangalore and worked in INOX multiplex cinema hall as a screen operator. He was drawing a salary of Rs. 30,000 and his life was running very smoothly. Suddenly everything changed due to COVID-19; all the cinema halls were closed across the country. He was bound to shift to his native place Bhubaneswar. After sitting idle for a month in his house, his savings completely drained out. Then, he borrowed some money from his father and started selling fruits, especially mango and guava, in a trolley near Rasuagarh market area and is now earning just 200 rupees per working day.

Prakash Samal, a pavbhaji seller in Bhubaneswar told us that everything was normal before COVID-19, and then everything changed. Due to fewer customers in the market, he is unable to survive as daily sales are much lesser than his previous average sales. There are six members in his family entirely depending on him. He also has a bank loan availed for his business, which he is unable to pay during the lockdown. Also, he is unable to pay his son's college and tuition fees. The living condition of his family has worsened.

India's National Policy on Urban Street Vendors

Historically, street vending was regulated by the state government and municipal officials with many actions taken against vendors. Street vending was regarded as an illegal activity as they traded in public or private places, block pavements, and sometimes created traffic problems. They were humiliated by government officials and suffered in different aspects. However, as they constituted a large group in the economy and most

vulnerable to uncertainty, laws were needed to help them. For this reason, national policies were formulated to protect the interest of street vendors. The first policy judgement regarding street vending in India was started in 1983 (Bombay hawker's association vs. Bombay municipal corporation case). In this appeal, the Bombay Municipal Corporation Act 1888 was challenged for its arbitrary and unguided power to refuse to grant or renew license for hawking and removal of products from the street. After two years, in 1985, Bombay Hawkers Association vs. Bombay Municipal Corporation case was filed with the aim that hawkers should be allowed to do business with strict regulation on adulteration. After that, in 1989, a classic judgement by the Supreme Court of India in the case of Sodan Singh vs. New Delhi municipal committee was issued that article 19 (1)(g) covers street vending; however, a reasonable restriction could be enforced by article 19(6) by the authority. And municipal authority will permit hawkers for roadside trading, but hawkers cannot make it a permanent asset. Later, in 2001, the Government of India declared a task force to report on street vending. After a short period, national policy on urban street venter was launched in 2004. In 2009, the national policy on urban street vendors was revised to promote livelihood of vendors and prevent overcrowding and unsanitary conditions in the streets. After four years, in 2013, the Supreme Court asked all state chief secretaries to constitute a town vending committee as per the 2009 policy. In 2014, the most important policy on street vendors (street vendors act, 2014) was passed by the parliament. The street vendors (protection of livelihood and regulation of street vending) Act, 2014, directs appropriate schemes and rules to be formulated by the government to benefit street vendors.

The street vendors (protection of livelihood and regulation of street vending) Act, 2014 directed to formulate town vending committee, which will be responsible for all vendors under its jurisdiction. The committee is to be formulated by 40 per cent of vendor participation and will facilitate dispute resolution by creating grievance redressal channels. All street vendors will be accommodated with a designated vending zone. Keeping in view the issue of child labour, all vendors above 14 years will be provided a certificate of vending. The authority has the power to take action against vendors violating norms and regulations. Despite the enactment of the act, no such impact has been noticed in the condition of street vendors (an interview of Bhowmik, an expert in urban poor and informal sector by SHRAM, 2015).

Government Initiatives for Street Vendors

COVID-19 is unprecedented health and economic crisis in which government intervention with the aim to minimize its adverse effects is important. The government is also adopting many measures to curtail its adverse effects on different groups of society. The Ministry of Labour and Employment (MOLE) has issued an advisory to employers of public and private establishments (including ministries and departments) to extend their coordination by not terminating their employees, particularly casual and contractual workers, from their job or reduce their wages (ILO, 2020). The central government has announced a special scheme related to micro credit facility namely PM SVANidhi i.e., Pradhan Mantri Street Vendors Atma Nirbhar Nidhi. This scheme was initiated by the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs to provide affordable land for street vendors to restore their livelihoods disrupted by announcement of COVID-19 lockdown on June 1, 2020. This scheme targets 50 lakh street vendors who shall receive a working capital loan of Rs. 10,000, which is repayable in monthly installments during tenure of one year. The benefit of interest subvention is also exists if the loan is paid on time through direct benefit transfer. Till now, 2,77,322 vendors have applied for this scheme, of which 29,566 have been approved. The Government of Odisha has announced a relief package of Rs. 3000 to 65,000 registered street vendors in 114 urban areas of the state amid the nationwide lockdown. Outreach of policy measures to curb the adverse effect of COVID-19 on different social groups is not equidistributed (Kesar et al., 2020).

4. Conclusion

Street vending is a critical occupation with job insecurity and poor working conditions. These vendors are facing many difficulties like low income and lack of sanitary measures at workplace. With these difficulties, the corona virus is spreading and the lockdown has deteriorated their living conditions to a worse level. The working opportunity for street vendors has declined due to several restrictions and lack of demand. More particularly, a significant amount of income has reduced for all street vendors due to the spread of coronavirus. Even globally, some cities like Mexico, Accra, Los Angeles, and New York, where vendors were allowed to vend, reported a 90 per cent drop in their income due to reduced foot traffic (Belbuena, 2020). So overall, the study concludes that life and livelihood of street vendors are badly affected due to the COVID-19 lockdown.

Suggestions for Street Vendors

- The Street Vendors Act 2014 is a groundbreaking effort to secure urban street vendors' livelihood and social security rights. This enables the government to eliminate poverty. The Act aims to create a friendly atmosphere for urban street vendors to do their businesses without harassment. However, the Act has not been enforced in many cities. In the few cities where law regulations have been enforced, the regulatory system has undermined the rule. Therefore, The Street Vendors Act (2014) should be implemented properly and speedily in all the states and union territories
- Street vendors represent one of the largest and most visible segments of the informal economy. The actual number of people employed as street vendors is largely unknown in our country. Government officials need reliable data on street vendors so that correct and efficient policies are formulated. There is an urgent need to create a database for the street vendors by competent institutions and public agencies. After collecting the database for the street vendors, the vendors should be issued identity card. This approach would increase the confidence of vendors in the local government and the mapping results.
- Land management is essential for improving urban planning. The street vendors constitute 2 per cent of the city's population. Thus, 2 per cent of every town's land should be allocated to street vendors. Compulsory arrangements must be made to allocate 2 per cent of the vending spaces in new city planning schemes for new areas. Detailed information of the local environment would help to incorporate updated street vendor designs on-site while solving emerging problems in allocating space to vendors.
- Street vending plays a critical role in ensuring livelihood to a large section of the underprivileged and marginalized society. The city administration or urban planning departments never recognize their contribution. Street vendors work under the persistent threat of municipal and police eviction. This strategy must be avoided to encourage street vendors to carry on business without fear of eviction.
- There is a high incidence of street vendors borrowing from money lenders in the study area. The government can assist them financially in their business activities at a free rate of interest. And the government can extend subsidy to the street vendors, especially for vending

perishable items. Bank initiatives must reduce this by supplying sufficient working capital at the economic expense and with minimal procedural delays. The government should provide interest-free loans, including MUDRA loans, with subsidies to street vendors.

- Vendors should have access to services such as clean drinking water, sanitation, electricity, and storage. These facilities would improve vendor profitability and help preserve hygiene and sanitation in the area.
- A state committee should be formed with members of several vendor associations.
- The analysis revealed that the research area lacks unionization among street vendors. Street vendors should organize and fight together for their cause and problems. NGOs can lead street vendors in this direction.
- Vendors' problems should be solved collectively through the participatory process of stakeholders, and strong legislation with guidelines should be enacted for the same.
- Monetary compensation should be given to street vendors to tide over the negative impact of COVID-19 and stimulate effective demand in the market.

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